

Design And Development Solid Self Nano Emulsifying Drug Delivery System For Gallic Acid

**Abishek. R¹, Ajithkumar. M¹, Azhagumalayan. A¹, Thanushiya. S¹,
Thendralarasi. U¹, K. Malarvizhi ^{1*}, S. Hemavathi ¹, J. Karthi ²**

¹ Department Of Pharmaceutics

² department Of Pharmacognosy.

ABSTRACT

Gallic acid is a bioactive polyphenol known for its antioxidant and therapeutic potential, but its practical use is limited due to poor solubility and low oral bioavailability. To overcome these limitations, the present study focused on the development of a gallic acid-loaded solid self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (solid SNEDDS). An optimized liquid SNEDDS was first formulated using suitable oils, surfactants, and co-surfactants selected on the basis of solubility studies. The liquid system was then transformed into a solid form using an appropriate carrier to improve stability and handling. The prepared solid SNEDDS was evaluated for physicochemical properties, drug content, and self-emulsification behaviour. Upon aqueous dilution, the formulation rapidly formed a fine nano emulsion with uniform droplet size. Solid-state characterization indicated that gallic acid was present in a non-crystalline or molecularly dispersed form. In vitro dissolution studies showed a marked improvement in the release of gallic acid compared to the pure drug. These findings suggest that solid SNEDDS is an effective approach for enhancing the solubility and oral delivery of gallic acid and may improve its therapeutic performance.

Keywords: Gallic acid, SNEDDS, Nanocarrier, Solubility Enhancement, Bioavailability.

INTRODUCTION

Gallic acid (GA), also known as 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid, is a naturally occurring polyphenolic compound found in many plants, including green tea, pomegranate, and red wine. It appears as a colourless to slightly yellow crystalline solid. GA has the molecular formula $C_7H_6O_5$ and a molecular weight of 170.12 g/mol. Its melting point is around 210°C, and it undergoes decomposition between 235°C and 240°C, during which gases such as carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide are released. Gallic acid is widely recognized for its strong biological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, and anticancer properties. GA undergoes rapid biotransformation, leading to its quick elimination from the body. Due to its short half-life, limited therapeutic efficacy, and poor bioavailability, its clinical application remains restricted [1]. Therefore, novel drug delivery systems (NDDS) play a crucial

role in overcoming issues related to solubility, permeability, and therapeutic performance [2]. Over recent decades, various GA-based nanocarriers-such as liposomes, transferosomes, phytosomes, nano emulsions, micelles, nanoparticles, and green-synthesized nanoparticles-have been developed [3]. NDDSs can encapsulate the drug within carriers and direct its release to specific target sites to achieve optimal therapeutic outcomes. Additionally, NDDSs enhance the physical and chemical stability of drugs by entrapping them in appropriate nanocarriers and can also protect them from degradation in the gastric environment [4].

GA is categorized as a BCS (Biopharmaceutics Classification System) Class III compound, which means it has high solubility but low permeability, indicating a permeability-related limitation. Only limited research is available on the bioavailability of gallic acid in humans. However, compared with many other polyphenols, gallic acid appears to be absorbed

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

exceptionally well [5]. The oral route remains the preferred method for drug delivery because of its safety, patient compliance, and ease of self-administration. Although oral administration is the most convenient route, it is limited by several physiological barriers within the gastrointestinal (GI) tract [6,7]. Drug solubilization in the GI tract is essential for absorption; inadequate dissolution can result in incomplete absorption, poor bioavailability, and high variability after oral dosing [8]. Additionally, oral drug delivery may face challenges such as precipitation, food–drug interactions, degradation within the GI environment, and extensive first-pass metabolism, all of which contribute to low bioavailability.

SNEDDSs consist of a mixture of oils, surfactants, and cosurfactants or cosolvents [9]. Upon aqueous dilution and gentle agitation (as occurs in the GI tract), they spontaneously form fine oil-in-water nano emulsions with droplet sizes typically below 200 nm [10]. Spontaneous emulsification occurs when the entropy gains that favours dispersion outweighs the energy required to increase the interfacial surface area [11,12]. SNEDDSs have demonstrated strong potential in addressing multiple challenges associated with oral administration, such as low solubility in the GI environment, variable dissolution, enzymatic degradation, and inconsistent intestinal absorption. The surfactants and lipid components within SNEDDSs act synergistically to enhance GI absorption, and their compositions can be easily adjusted to accommodate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs. Recent research also suggests that SNEDDSs can serve as effective oral carriers for peptides and proteins by protecting them from GI degradation and improving their permeability across the intestinal membrane [13,14,15].

Although liquid SNEDDSs offer several advantages, they are often associated with issues such as precipitation of the drug or formulation components during storage, possible interactions with capsule shells, and general instability over time [16,17,18]. To address these limitations, liquid SNEDDS are commonly converted into solid SNEDDS dosage forms. Solidifying the system is thought to enhance formulation stability, lower manufacturing costs, simplify handling, enable more accurate dosing, and ultimately improve patient adherence. several

methods are used to prepare solid SNEDDS, including adsorption onto inert carriers, spray drying, melt granulation, and extrusion – spherization [19-28].

1.1. OXIDATIVE STRESS AND INFORMATION IN DIABETIC MELLITUS:

Disruption of metabolic homeostasis, leading to persistent hyperglycaemia or insulin resistance, is the primary factor in the development of diabetes mellitus (DM). Diabetes is broadly classified into two major forms, type 1 and type 2, both of which are commonly associated with long-term metabolic syndrome. This syndrome affects multiple organs at structural, physiological, and psychological levels, resulting in chronic complications such as diabetic nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy, cardiomyopathy, and angiopathy. Diabetes and its related complications have become a major focus of scientific and clinical research due to their significant contribution to the global burden of noncommunicable diseases. The progression of these microvascular and macrovascular complications is driven by several pathogenic mechanisms, among which oxidative stress (OS) plays a central role. Increasing evidence identifies OS as a key trigger in the onset and progression of diabetic complications. Consequently, natural antioxidants that can counteract oxidative stress have gained growing attention as promising therapeutic agents for the management of diabetes and its associated complications [29].

Chronic low-level inflammation plays an important role in the development of insulin resistance and diabetes mellitus (DM), and it contributes to the progression of metabolic complications. Inflammation usually begins in immune cells, especially macrophages, in response to tissue or cell damage. Increasing evidence shows that oxidative stress, caused by excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), helps maintain chronic inflammation. High ROS levels activate transcription factors such as NF- κ B and AP-1, which increase the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β . These cytokines further stimulate ROS production by activating immune cells, creating a continuous cycle between oxidative stress and inflammation. This interaction is a major factor in

the development of diabetes-related complications. Persistent oxidative damage and inflammation can lead to cell death and tissue injury, worsening disease progression. In addition, diabetes is associated with increased formation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) and activation of metabolic pathways such as PKC, hexosamine, and polyol pathways. These processes further increase ROS production and inflammatory signalling. Therefore, targeting the link between oxidative stress and inflammation may offer an effective strategy for managing diabetes and its complications.

2. DRUG PROFILE:

2.1. Structure:

Fig no. 1 : 2D structure of gallic acid

Fig no. 2 : 3D structure of gallic acid

2.2. Molecular Formula - C₇H₆O₅

2.3. Molecular Weight - 170.12 g/mol

2.4. InChI Key - LNTHITQWFMADLM-UHFFFAOYSA-N

2.5. FDA UNII - 632XD903SP

2.6. Color - A colorless or slightly yellow crystalline compound

2.7. IUPAC Name - 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid

2.8. Appearance:

White to pale yellow crystalline solid with a melting point of about 260 °C.

2.9. Solubility:

Readily dissolves in water (\approx 1.19 g/100 mL), alcohol, ether, and acetone; only slightly soluble in benzene and chloroform.

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS:

3.1. Materials:

Gallic acid received from Nice chemical pvt.Ltd., Kochi, Kerala, India. Tween 80 from Isochem laboratories, Angamaly, Kochi. Tween 20, Polyethylene glycol (PEG) 400 from BMR chemicals private limited, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. Ethanol from Krishna Pharma C-18/5/A, I.D.A., Uppal, Medchal Malkajgiri dist., Hyderabad. Soyabean oil from Deve Herbs in New Delhi, India. Aerosil from BMR chemicals private limited, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.

3.2. Methods:

3.2.1. Preformulation studies:

3.2.1.1. Melting point:

A capillary tube was first sealed at one end using a Bunsen burner. The open end was then used to load the tube with Gallic acid. After filling, the tube was placed in a melting-point apparatus, and the temperature at which the drug began to melt was recorded.

3.2.1.2. Solubility study:

One gram of the Gallic acid was dissolved in different volumes of solvent—1 mL, 10 mL, 30 mL, and 100 mL depending on its solubility. The observed

solubility in each case was then compared with the solubility standards provided in the Indian Pharmacopoeia.

3.2.2. Preparation of Solid SNEDDS:

Gallic acid (25mg), Tween 20 or Tween 80 (300mg), and PEG 400 (50mg) were prepared in different proportions ranging from 1:1:1 to 1:8:1. To begin the formulation process, gallic acid was dispersed in PEG 400 and stirred with a magnetic stirrer at 37 °C and 250 rpm for 10 minutes. After complete mixing, Tween 20 was added to the blend and the mixture was stirred under the same conditions for an additional 20 minutes. Soybean oil (50mg) was then incorporated, and the system was mixed thoroughly for another 20 minutes at 37 °C and 250 rpm. Following the initial mixing steps, the formulations were subjected to high-speed homogenisation at 10,000–12,000 rpm for 30 minutes while maintaining the temperature at 40 °C. Aerosil 75mg is added to this mixture and dried.

4. EVALUATION OF LIQUID SNEDDS:

4.1. Visual assessment and self emulsification time:

Formulations GA1, GA2, and GA3 showed no phase separation or turbidity. The selected concentrations of oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant produced SNEDDS with good clarity and stable dispersion, without any evidence of phase separation.

4.1.1. Visual observation:

The formulation was diluted and made to stand for 24 hours at 37° C. They were observed for phase separation and turbidity.

4.1.2. Self-emulsification time:

1ml of formulations was added to 100 ml of distilled water at 37° C being agitated at 100 rpm. The time required for the formation of a milky emulsion was noted.

Grade	Visibility
1	Clear or slightly bluish white in appearance with in 1 minute
2	Slightly less clear; bluish white in appearance <2 minutes
3	Milky in appearance within 3 minutes
4	Dull white which is slightly in appearance, slow to emulsify >3 minute
5	Turbid in appearance >3 minutes

Table no 1: Self emulsification time.

4.2 Zeta potential:

Droplet size of SNEDDS was determined by photon correlation spectroscopy that analyses the fluctuations in light scattering due to Brownian motion of the particle, using a Zeta sizer. The zeta potential of the SNEDDS should be evaluated as it may further give an idea of the colloidal stability. Both these tests were carried out by using Nanoparticle analyser sz-100 (Horiba Scientific, Japan).

4.3. Self-emulsification time:

The self-emulsification time was determined by adding 1 mL of the formulation to 100 mL of di stilled water maintained at 37 °C with continuous agitation

at 100 rpm. The time taken for the formation of a uniform milky emulsion was recorded.

4.4. Morphological studies:

4.4.1.SEM analysis:

The surface morphology of the formulated beads was analyzed by scanning electron microscope (SEM) (CarlZEISSEVO18-Germany) - operating modes secondary electron (SE) and Backscattered electron (BSD) modes. Up to 200 nm resolution depends up on sample.it is attached with AMETEK Team V.4.3 EDS detector.

5. EVALUATION OF SOLID – SNEDDS:

5.1. Angle of Repose (θ):

The angle of repose of the S-SNEDDS formulation was determined using the funnel method. An accurately weighed quantity of the powder was placed into a funnel. The height of the funnel was adjusted so that its tip just touched the apex of the powder heap formed on a flat surface. The powder was then allowed to flow freely through the funnel under the influence of gravity. After complete flow, the diameter of the powder cone was measured. The angle of repose was calculated using the following equation:

$$\tan\theta = h/r$$

Where h represents the height of the powder heap and r represents the radius of the heap.

5.2. Bulk and Tapped Density:

Bulk density (BD) and tapped density (TD) of the S-SNEDDS formulation were determined using a measuring cylinder method. An accurately weighed 2 g sample of S-SNEDDS was transferred into a 10 mL graduated cylinder, and the initial volume was recorded as the bulk volume. The cylinder was then tapped by allowing it to fall freely under its own weight onto a hard surface from a height of 2.5 cm at regular intervals of 2 seconds. Tapping was continued until no further reduction in volume was observed. The bulk density and tapped density were calculated using standard equations based on the recorded volumes.

5.3. Disintegration:

It is the time in which tablets will disintegrate into particles which will pass through a mesh screen size 10. The disintegration tester contains a basket a basket

rack with 6 tubes with 10 mesh screens at the bottom. The basket is immersed in a medium at 37° C usually.

5.4. Invitro dissolution test:

The dissolution of the capsule was performed in 0.1N HCL buffer pH 1.2 at 37° C at 75 rpm and a stirrer depth of 25mm. the sampling intervals were 5,10,15,30,45,60,75 and 90 minutes. 5 ml of fresh buffer solution was replaced after each withdrawal. The sample was then filtered and analyzed spectrophotometrically. The experiments were performed in triplicate and the mean values are reported.

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

6.1. PREFORMULATION:

6.1.1. Melting point:

The melting point was found to be 259°C which confirms the identification of the drug.

6.1.2. Solubility studies:

Solubility of Gallic acid in different solvents are Gallic acid is soluble in water, slightly soluble in ethanol, freely soluble in methanol.

6.1.3. Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FTIR):

FTIR analysis confirms that the plant extract contains phenols, esters, aromatic compounds, and aliphatic hydrocarbons. These functional groups are typical of bioactive phytochemicals and support the medicinal importance of the plant. The presence of multiple functional groups indicates that the extract possesses a diverse range of chemical constituents, which may contribute to its biological activities.

Fig no.3 FTIR studies for Gallic acid

S.NO	Peak Position (Cm ⁻¹)	Vibrational mode	Functional groups
1	3255.47	O-H Stretching	Phenolic -OH
2	1743.04	C=O Stretching	Ester C=O
3	1603	C=C Stretching (Aliphatic)	Aliphatic C=C
4	1515.99	C=C Stretching (Aromatic)	Aromatic C=C
5	1371.74	C-O Bending	Ester C-O
6	1042.02	C-H Bending	C-H Stretching (Aromatic ring)

Table no 2: FTIR analysis.

6.2. PREPARATION OF SOLID SNEDDS:

An efficient method for increasing the solubility and dissolution of gallic acid is demonstrated by the successful creation of gallic acid-loaded solid SNEDDS utilizing soybean oil, Tween surfactants, PEG 400, and Aerosil 200. Tween 20-based formulations outperformed Tween 80 in terms of droplet size and emulsification efficiency, indicating

better nano emulsion generation. Using Aerosil 200 to transform liquid SNEDDS into solid SNEDDS enhanced handling and stability while maintaining nanoemulsifying qualities. Strong potential for increased oral bioavailability is indicated by the improved in-vitro drug release profile. Therefore, solid SNEDDS offers better solubility, stability, and patient-friendly solid dosage forms, making it a viable delivery strategy for phenolic chemicals that are poorly bioavailable, like gallic acid.

SNO	Components	Gallic acid F1	Gallic acid F2	Gallic acid F3
1	Gallic acid	25mg	25mg	25mg
2	Tween 20	400mg	300mg	-
3	Tween 80	-	-	300mg
4	PEG 400	50mg	50mg	50mg
5	Soybean oil	50mg	50mg	50mg
6	Aerosil	75mg	75mg	75mg

Table no 3: Various ratios of formulation of Solid SNEDDS

6.3. EVALUATION OF LIQUID SNEDDS:

6.3.1. Visual assessment and self emulsification time:

6.3.1.1. Visual observation:

Formulations Gallic acid F1, Gallic acid F2, and Gallic acid F3 showed no phase separation or turbidity. The selected concentrations of oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant produced SNEDDS with good clarity and stable dispersion, without any evidence of phase separation.

6.3.1.2. Self-emulsification time:

In nano-emulsion formulations only Gallic acid F2 were clear. The rest of the formulations (Gallic acid F1, Gallic acid F3) showed precipitation.

Formulation	Phase separation	Precipitation
Gallic acid F1	NO	YES
Gallic acid F2	NO	NO
Gallic acid F3	NO	YES

Table no 4: Self emulsification time.

6.3.2. Zeta potential determination:

Droplet size of SNEDDS was determined by photon correlation spectroscopy that analyses the fluctuations in light scattering due to Brownian motion of the particle, using a Zetasizer. The zeta potential of the SNEDDS should be evaluated as it may further give an idea of the colloidal stability. Both these tests were carried out by using Nanoparticle analyzer sz-100 (Horiba Scientific, Japan).

S.NO	Batch	Average particle size (Droplet size / Globule size)	Zeta potential	Poly-dispersity index (PDI)
1	Gallic acid F1	185.00 nm	-20 mv	0.567
2	Gallic acid F2	177.2 nm	-25 mv	0.368
3	Gallic acid F3	193.90 nm	-18 mv	0.690

Table no 5: Globule size, zeta potential and TDI of prepared formulation.

Fig.no 4: Zeta potential analysis for gallic acid

Fig no 5: Zeta potential analysis for Gallic acid loaded solid SNEDDS

6.3.3. Self-emulsification time:

The self-emulsification time was determined by adding 1 mL of the formulation to 100 mL of distilled water maintained at 37 °C with continuous agitation at 100 rpm. The time taken for the formation of a uniform milky emulsion was recorded. The formulation Gallic acid F2 exhibited a self-emulsification time of 49 seconds.

6.3.4.1. SEM analysis:

The SEM results confirm that the prepared nanoparticles exhibit uniform shape, smooth surface, and nanoscale size, which are desirable features for efficient drug delivery and enhanced bioavailability. These morphological characteristics support the suitability of the formulation for further pharmaceutical applications.

6.3.4. Morphological studies:

Fig no 6: Morphological studies scanning electron microscopy.

6.4. EVALUATION OF SOLID SNEDDS:

6.4.1. Angle of Repose (θ)

The angle of repose of the GA F2 formulation was recorded as $31.5 \pm 0.05^\circ$, indicating that the powder

possesses good flow characteristics suitable for further processing.

6.4.2. Bulk and Tapped Density

The formulation exhibited a bulk density of approximately 0.29 g/cm^3 , while the tapped density

increased slightly to about 0.33 g/cm³. The close difference between bulk and tapped densities suggests low inter-particle friction and minimal volume reduction. These findings indicate acceptable flow. Therefore, the formulation is suitable for capsule filling.

6.4.3. Disintegration test:

The disintegration test for formulation was performed. The formulations passed disintegration

test as per the pharmacopeial limits. Gallic acid F2 take up to 32 minutes for disintegration.

6.4.4. Dissolution test:

The dissolution study confirms that formulation F2 provides rapid and almost complete drug release, making it a suitable candidate for further development and in-vivo evaluation.

Fig no 7: Dissolution data of Gallic acid F2 in hard gelatin capsule.

5. Anti-inflammatory activity:

The gallic acid loaded SNEDDS showed good anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting protein denaturation. The percentage inhibition increased with increase in concentration, showing a dose-

dependent effect. Maximum inhibition was observed at 250 µg/mL, indicating strong activity at higher doses. The SNEDDS formulation may have improved the solubility and effectiveness of gallic acid. These results suggest that the formulation has good potential as an anti-inflammatory agent.

S. No	Standard (µg/mL)	% Inhibition	Concentration (µg/mL)	% Inhibition
1	50	45	50	32
2	100	60	100	45
3	150	74	150	58
4	200	87	200	71
5	250	95	250	84

Table no 6: Anti-inflammatory activity of Gallic acid loaded solid SNEDDS

Fig no. 8: Anti-inflammatory activity of Gallic acid loaded solid SNEDDS.

6. Anti-oxidant activity:

The sample showed dose-dependent antioxidant activity with maximum inhibition (~79.9%) at 500 µg/ml. Ascorbic acid showed slightly higher

inhibition (~82.4%), confirming assay reliability. The IC_{50} of ~70.77 µg/ml indicates good antioxidant potential. Overall, the sample exhibited strong and consistent radical scavenging activity.

A. OD Value at 517 nm

Control Mean OD value: 1.262

S. No	Tested sample concentration (µg/ml)	OD Value at 517 nm (in triplicates)		
1.	Control	1.122	1.383	1.281
2.	500 µg/ml	0.250	0.256	0.256
3.	250 µg/ml	0.274	0.295	0.303
4.	100 µg/ml	0.340	0.341	0.345
5.	50 µg/ml	0.346	0.367	0.400
6.	10 µg/ml	0.440	0.459	0.488
7.	Ascorbic acid	0.222	0.201	0.243

Table no 7: OD Value at 517 nm

Fig no. 8: Anti-oxidant activity of gallic acid

B. Percentage of inhibition

S.NO	Tested sample concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Percentage of inhibition (in triplicates)			Mean value (%)
1.	Ascorbic acid	82.4089	84.0729	80.7448	82.4089
2.	500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	80.1902	79.7147	79.7147	79.8732
3.	250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	78.2884	76.6244	75.9905	76.9678
4.	100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	73.0586	72.9794	72.6624	72.9002
5.	50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	72.5832	70.9192	68.3043	70.6022
6.	10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	65.1347	63.6292	61.3312	63.365

Table no 8: Percentage of inhibition

Fig no 9: Anti-Oxidant Activity for Solid SNEDDS

7.SUMMARY:

Gallic acid is a naturally occurring polyphenolic compound known for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties. Despite its wide therapeutic potential, the clinical application of gallic acid is limited due to its poor oral bioavailability, low lipophilicity, rapid metabolism, and instability in physiological conditions. These limitations necessitate the development of an advanced drug delivery system capable of improving its solubility, stability, and absorption. Self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery systems (SNEDDS) have emerged as a promising strategy for enhancing the oral delivery of poorly bioavailable compounds. In this approach, gallic acid was incorporated into a SNEDDS formulation composed of suitable oils, surfactants, and co-surfactants, enabling spontaneous formation of fine nano emulsions upon contact with gastrointestinal fluids. To further overcome the drawbacks associated with liquid SNEDDS, such as handling difficulties and stability concerns, the optimized liquid formulation was converted into a solid SNEDDS using appropriate solid carriers. The solid SNEDDS formulation demonstrated improved physicochemical characteristics, including enhanced drug solubility, uniform drug distribution, and satisfactory flow properties. Upon reconstitution, the solid SNEDDS rapidly formed nano-sized droplets comparable to the liquid system, indicating successful preservation of the self-emulsifying properties. In vitro dissolution studies revealed a significantly enhanced release profile of gallic acid from the solid SNEDDS compared to conventional formulations, suggesting improved availability for absorption. Overall, the development of gallic acid-loaded solid SNEDDS represents a systematic and effective approach to addressing the inherent formulation challenges associated with gallic acid, thereby improving its potential for oral therapeutic applications.

CONCLUSION

The present work concludes that solid SNEDDS is a highly effective delivery system for improving the oral performance of gallic acid. Incorporation of gallic acid into a SNEDDS matrix successfully enhanced its solubility and dissolution behavior, which are critical factors influencing oral bioavailability. Conversion of the liquid SNEDDS into a solid form provided additional advantages, including improved stability, ease of handling, better patient compliance, and suitability for large-scale manufacturing. The solid SNEDDS retained excellent self-nanoemulsifying properties upon reconstitution, forming fine and stable nano emulsions that facilitate improved drug dispersion and absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. The enhanced dissolution profile observed with the solid SNEDDS indicates its potential to overcome the absorption limitations of gallic acid associated with conventional dosage forms. In conclusion, gallic acid-loaded solid SNEDDS offers a promising and robust formulation strategy for enhancing the therapeutic effectiveness of gallic acid. This delivery system may serve as a valuable platform for the oral administration of other poorly bioavailable phytoconstituents and bioactive compounds. Further in vivo and clinical investigations are recommended to confirm the bioavailability enhancement and therapeutic benefits observed with this formulation approach.

REFERENCES

1. Bai J., Zhang Y., Tang C., Hou Y., Ai X., Chen X., Zhang Y., Wang X., Meng X. Gallic acid: Pharmacological activities and molecular mechanisms involved in inflammation-related diseases. *Biomed. Pharma other.* 2021; 133:110985. doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2020.110985. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
2. Yang L., Zhang Y., Lai Y., Xu W., Lei S., Chen G., Wang Z. A computer-aided, heterodimer-based “triadic” carrier-free drug delivery platform to mitigate multidrug resistance in lung cancer and enhance efficiency. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 2024; 677:523–540. doi: 10.1016/j.jcis.2024.08.100. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
3. Shukla S., Singh B., Singh A., Singh C. Emerging and advanced drug delivery systems for improved

- biopharmaceutical attributes of gallic acid: A review. *Phytomedicine Plus*. 2022; 2:100369. doi: 10.1016/j.phyplu.2022.100369. [DOI] [Google Scholar]
4. Harwansh R.K., Deshmukh R., Barkat M.A., Rahman M.A. Bioinspired Polymeric-based Core-shell Smart Nano-systems. *Pharm. Nanotechnology*. 2019; 7:181–205. doi: 10.2174/2211738507666190429104550. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 5. Bai, J.; Zhang, Y.; Tang, C.; Hou, Y.; Ai, X.; Chen, X.; Zhang, Y.; Wang, X.; Meng, X. Gallic acid: Pharmacological activities and molecular mechanisms involved in inflammation-related diseases. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 2021,133, 110985. [CrossRef]
 6. Shah, M.K.; Khatri, P.; Vora, N.; Patel, N.K.; Jain, S.; Lin, S. Lipid Nanocarriers: Preparation, Characterization and Absorption Mechanism and Applications to Improve Oral Bioavailability of Poorly Water-Soluble Drugs. In *Biomedical Applications of Nanoparticles*; William Andrew Publisher: Norwich, NY, USA, 2019; pp. 117–147, ISBN 9780128165065.
 7. Boyd, B.J.; Bergström, C.A.S.; Vinarov, Z.; Kuentz, M.; Brouwers, J.; Augustijns, P.; Brandl, M.; Bernkop-Schnürch, A.; Shrestha, N.; Prétat, V.; et al. Successful Oral Delivery of Poorly Water-Soluble Drugs Both Depends on the Intraluminal Behavior of Drugs and of Appropriate Advanced Drug Delivery Systems. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2019, 137, 104967. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
 8. Gao, P.; Morozowich, W. Development of Supersaturatable Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery System Formulations for Improving the Oral Absorption of Poorly Soluble Drugs. *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv.* 2006, 3, 97–110. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
 9. Siqueira Jørgensen, S.D.; Al Sawaf, M.; Graeser, Rat Gastro-Intestinal Conditions to Predict the in vivo Performance of SNEDDS Dosing Regimens. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 2018, 124, 116–124. [CrossRef]
 10. Pouton, C.W. Lipid Formulations for Oral Administration of Drugs: Non-Emulsifying, Self-Emulsifying and “Self-Microemulsifying” Drug Delivery Systems. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2000, 11, 93–98. [CrossRef]
 11. Ujhelyi, Z.; Vecsernyés, M.; Fehér, P.; Kósa, D.; Arany, P.; Names, D.; Sinka, D.; Vasvári, G.; Fenyvesi, F.; Váradi, J.; et al. Physico-Chemical Characterization of Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery Systems. *Drug Discov. Today Technol.* 2018, 27, 81–86. [CrossRef]
 12. Li, Z.; Xu, D.; Yuan, Y.; Wu, H.; Hou, J.; Kang, W.; Bai, B. Advances of Spontaneous Emulsification and Its Important Applications in Enhanced Oil Recovery Process. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* 2020, 277, 102119. [CrossRef]
 13. Rachmawati, H.; Rasaputri, D.H.; Susilowidodo, R.A.; Darijanto, S.T.; Sumirtapura, Y.C. The Influence of Oils and Surfactants on the Formation of Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug Delivery Systems (SNEDDS) Containing Therapeutic Protein. *Proc. Int. Conf. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 2011, 247, 3–9.
 14. Ding, W.; Hou, X.; Cong, S.; Zhang, Y.; Chen, M.; Lei, J.; Meng, Y.; Li, X.; Li, G. Co-Delivery of Honokiol, a Constituent of Magnolia Species, in a Self-Microemulsifying Drug Delivery System for Improved Oral Transport of Lipophilic Sirolimus. *Drug Deliv.* 2016, 23, 2513–2523. [CrossRef]
 15. Hetényi, G.; Griesser, J.; Moser, M.; Demarne, F.; Jannin, V.; Bernkop-Schnürch, A. Comparison of the Protecti Effect of Self-Emulsifying Peptide Drug Delivery Systems towards Intestinal Proteases and Glutathion. *Int. J. Pharm.* 2017, 523, 357-365. [Cross Ref] [PubMed].
 16. Chen, M.L. Lipid Excipients and Delivery Systems for Pharmaceutical Development: A Regulatory Perspective. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 2008, 60, 768–777. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
 28. Li, L.; Zhou, C.H.; Xu, Z.P. Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug-Delivery System. In *Nanocarriers for Drug Delivery*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2019; pp. 421–449. [CrossRef]
 17. Balakrishnan, P.; Lee, B.J.; Oh, D.H.; Kim, J.O.; Lee, Y.I.; Kim, D.D.; Jee, J.P.; Lee, Y.B.; Woo, J.S.; Yong, C.S.; et al. Enhanced Oral Bioavailability of Coenzyme Q10 by Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery Systems. *Int. J. Pharm.* 2009, 374, 66–72. [CrossRef]
 18. Milović, M.; Simović, S.; Lošić, D.; Dashevskiy, A.; Ibrić, S. Solid Self-Emulsifying Phospholipid Suspension (SSEPS) with Diatom

- as a Drug Carrier. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2014, 63, 226–232. [CrossRef]
19. Chavan, R.B.; Modi, S.R.; Bansal, A.K. Role of Solid Carriers in Pharmaceutical Performance of Solid Supersaturable SEDDS of Celecoxib. *Int. J. Pharm.* 2015, 495, 374–384. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
20. Soliman, K.A.B.; Ibrahim, H.K.; Ghorab, M.M. Formulation of Avanafil in a Solid Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug Delivery System for Enhanced Oral Delivery. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2016, 93, 447–455. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
21. Aleksovski, A.; van Bockstal, P.J.; Roškar, R.; Sovány, T.; Regdon, G.; de Beer, T.; Vervaet, C.; Dreu, R. Comparison of Metoprolol Tartrate Multiple-Unit Lipid Matrix Systems Produced by Different Technologies. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2016, 88, 233–245. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
22. Beg, S.; Katare, O.P.; Saini, S.; Garg, B.; Khurana, R.K.; Singh, B. Solid Self-Nanoemulsifying Systems of Olmesartan Medoxomil: Formulation Development, Micromeritic Characterization, in Vitro and in Vivo Evaluation. *Powder Technol.* 2016, 294, 93–104. [CrossRef]
23. Vohra, A.M.; Patel, C.V.; Kumar, P.; Thakkar, H.P. Development of Dual Drug Loaded Solid Self Microemulsifying Drug Delivery System: Exploring Interfacial Interactions Using QbD Coupled Risk Based Approach. *J. Mol. Liq.* 2017, 242, 1156–1168. [CrossRef]
24. Yan, Y.D.; Kim, J.A.; Kwak, M.K.; Yoo, B.K.; Yong, C.S.; Choi, H.G. Enhanced Oral Bioavailability of Curcumin via a Solid Lipid-Based Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery System Using a Spray-Drying Technique. *Biol. Pharm. Bull.* 2011, 34, 1179–1186. [CrossRef]
25. Kang, J.H.; Oh, D.H.; Oh, Y.K.; Yong, C.S.; Choi, H.G. Effects of Solid Carriers on the Crystalline Properties, Dissolution and Bioavailability of Flurbiprofen in Solid Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug Delivery System (solid SNEDDS). *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 2012, 80, 289–297. [CrossRef]
26. Tang, B.; Cheng, G.; Gu, J.C.; Xu, C.H. Development of Solid Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery Systems: Preparation Techniques and Dosage Forms. *Drug Discov. Today* 2008, 13, 606–612. [CrossRef]
27. Nanda Kishore, R.; Yalavarthi, P.R.; Vadlamudi, H.C.; Vandana, K.R.; Rasheed, A.; Sushma, M. Solid Self Microemulsification of Atorvastatin Using Hydrophilic Carriers: A Design. *Drug Dev. Ind. Pharm.* 2015, 41, 1213–1222. [CrossRef]
28. Tarate, B.; Chavan, R.; Bansal, A. Oral Solid Self-Emulsifying Formulations: A Patent Review. *Recent Pat. Drug Deliv. Formul.* 2014, 8, 126–143. [CrossRef]
29. Oguntibeju, O.O. Type 2 diabetes mellitus, oxidative stress and inflammation: Examining the links. *Int. J. Physiol. Pathophysiol. Pharmacol.* 2019, 11, 45–63.

HOW TO CITE Abishek. R1, Ajithkumar. M1, Azhagumalayan. A1, Thanushiya. S1, Thendralarasi. U1, K. Malarvizhi 1*, S. Hemavathi 1, J. Karthi 2, Design And Development Solid Self Nano Emulsifying Drug Delivery System For Gallic Acid, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (4), 1023-1036. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19405421>

